

**AN ANALYSIS ON THE CARBON TAX'S
CONTRIBUTIONS TO FREE MARKET
SOCIETIES AND ITS PERSONAGES**

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First proposed in 1973 by British MIT academic David Gordon, the carbon tax is a radical economic policy aimed at tackling the fiscal burden of CO₂ emissions; considered a 'negative externality' in free-market economics. Built upon analysis of the 'Social Cost of Carbon' to calculate numeric externalities, in tandem with considering the utilization of revenue gained from this policy, this polarising economical concept has gone from simply another environmental idea, to being implemented in over 40 sovereign states, affecting the citizens of each whilst remaining an essential propagator for partisan divergence within political systems internationally. Upon analysis of its effects on the private and public sectors globally, common, yet misguided beliefs arise in regards to its beneficial elements, such as that the implementation of the Carbon Tax has provided positive reform globally through its supposed ability to enumerate and quantify the typically immeasurable social cost of CO₂ emissions, reduce the emissions of the prominent greenhouse gas, and reduce the adverse economics effects on day-to-day citizens within employment. Despite these claims, analysis of the tax's inability to tackle other greenhouse gasses, its consistent negative targeting toward lower-income neighbourhoods, and its tendency to establish a lucrative relationship between prospering high-emission and unregulated lower-income nations in a form of carbon leakage, calls for either huge reforms of the tax, or a complete overhaul, where better alternatives to combat the climate crisis should stand in.

One praise of the tax is its ability to enumerate the social cost of carbon; an inherently difficult economical liability to quantify, given subjective and fluctuational elements. Despite this, the SCC vigorously considers the magnitude of destruction and cost of remedy, to determine the figure which society pays per carbon tonne produced, utilised by legislatures when considering the tax on CO₂. Statistical analysis for the SCC's influence on carbon tax has led to praise over a seemingly robust system, wherein it includes collaboration between the IPCC, EPA, and various universities over

decades of research. However, closer analysis reveals the ineffectiveness of the SCC at influencing the carbon tax. While conceptual theory emphasises importance of direct linkage between the tax and SCC, political rebuttal often leads to fatally ineffective differences; the 2024 SCC was around \$1000/tCO₂, whilst the tax was only \$160/tCO₂, \$840 of untaxed omissions per tCO₂. Combined with unreliable variations of SCC, where a 2021 Nature study determined a range of 10-800 USD/tCO₂, it is evident that the SCC is unable to determine 'fair' carbon taxations, exposing fatal flaws within the wider system.

Another shortsighted praise regarding carbon tax is its ability to reduce emissions towards targets below 2°C above pre-industrial averages, per the Paris Agreement. The greenhouse-gas is considered a propagator of climate change, which the tax accosts via means of incentivisation and deterration; an added liability on lucrative forms of fuel production deters companies from slimmer profit margins, and incentivises a transition toward profitable, cleaner, and taxation-free energy. The UK's implementation of carbon taxation on electricity showed energy reductions of 18%, and usage decreasing 23%, with similar reductions globally. However, these reductions fail to confront Paris Agreement goals; IPCC claims a 43% emission reduction by 2030 is needed to achieve this, yet 2022 GtCO₂ levels were 36.6, oppositionary to the 20 GtCO₂, which is required by 2030. Current trajectories suggest average reductions of <1%/annum, significantly smaller than the required 4.5%/annum. Despite hefty carbon tax implementations, emission deductions fall evidently short of the Paris Agreement, an inherent flaw within the carbon tax which calls for immediate reform.

Carbon tax is often-times hailed as the economic strategy with the least adverse effects on day-to-day citizens, regarding employment. Common concerns regarding the introduction of environmentally-targeted economic concepts is their effect on the working-class. However, British Columbia research in 2020, which has implemented the carbon tax since 2008, proved an increase of

employment post-tax introduction; local businesses increased employment rates, and jobs lost at pollutant-production industries were equally replaced with green-sector jobs. Utilisations of tax revenue has helped propagate alternative employment areas, including the Alberta Coal Transition Programme, a government-funded programme assisting coal-workers in employment transition. However, whilst carbon tax encourages a movement toward green-energy employment, it fails to acknowledge detrimental impacts upon the non-renewable energy sector. A 2022 MIT study found potential US carbon taxes would lead to employment decreases of 2.24%, while green-energy employment would only rise by 1.04%, leading millions into unemployment. Similarly, a 2021 Deloitte report depicted up to 1.4 million jobs at risk due to these policies within Canada. It is evident that carbon tax bears a weighty responsibility of constructing new jobs in place of countless damaged workforces across its countries, raising concerns over its overall integrity, and associated responsibilities that come alongside the tax.

Opposingly, an inherent flaw of the carbon tax is its limited targeting nature; The tax utilises heavy funding to tackle climate change through one specific emission, yet propagates underminement over multitudes of other greenhouse gases, which also pose devastating consequences. Some mistakenly claim a much-needed importance on CO₂ removal, given it accounts for 80% of U.S. greenhouse gas emissions, and 64% of the global warming effects faced today. Conversely, while CO₂ is the most abundant greenhouse gas, the other 3 gases compensate this through their harsher properties; On its own, methane is 30 times stronger than CO₂, one pound of nitrous oxide warms the atmosphere 300 times more than carbon does over a century, and fluorinated gases are the most potent, longest-lasting greenhouse gases overall. The carbon tax's higher aim of preventing climate change is evidently superseded by its ignorance of more lethal emissions; made worse through diverting attention away from these

deadly gases, both socially and economically, given its dominance in the media and heavy funding, which calls for a reform of this matter.

Carbon taxes also consistently and unfairly target lower-income communities through propagation of the cost-of-living crisis. While it is erroneously believed that high-income households pay the most for carbon tax due to a relatively higher CO₂ emission output, and welfare states such as Sweden's and Canada's can be implemented to balance out inequalities, it is apparent that the tax still heavily impacts vulnerable communities. A 2021 BLS study found energy costs accounted for 7-8% of expenditures for low-income households, compared to 2-3% for high-income households, which poses possible class disproportions in paying a carbon tax, exacerbated by the inherent inability of lower-income households to transition to expensive, greener energy sources, which the IMF concluded based on this that policies of the carbon tax regressively and disproportionately affect low-income CO₂-producing areas. It is clear that this taxation forces vulnerable communities to bear the brunt of higher emissions outputted by wealthier groups, and the implementation requires heavier maintenance of a welfare state to prevent such oppression, raising questions on the effectiveness of the tax.

Lastly, the carbon tax implementation has led to an unequal and lucrative form of 'Carbon Leakage'; a reactionary practise whereby emissions are pushed from wealthier, regulated nations onto underdeveloped and taxless ones, in what often leads to a decrease of effectiveness in emission reduction (positive leakage). While some may claim that leakage results in reduced demand for coal, oil, and gas in developed countries, whilst allowing developing countries to substitute CO₂-emitters for coal, which lowers emissions, and that leakage is a core element of environmental economics, seen within the 2030 Energy and Climate Framework and the European-Union's carbon leakage list, it is opposingly

prominent that despite an ability to shift developing countries away from carbon emissions short-term, a failure to innovate less-polluting technologies would lead to this shift in smaller nations to be meaningless overall.

Conclusively, it is evident that while the carbon tax may propose some positive environmental reforms, such as through its decades-old academic studies in calculating the SCC, its apparent ability at somewhat decreasing emissions, and all whilst steadily maintaining the job market, there is an overwhelming amount of factors which expose its inherent flaws, such as its undermining of more significantly dangerous greenhouse-gases, a consistent targeting of lower-income communities, and a constructed unequal parity between developed and underdeveloped nations, all pointing to a wider need of a better system in hopes of economically combating climate change. Fortunately, better systems exist in place of carbon tax. Carbon-Emissions-Trading caps emission levels